

**THE SIGNIFICANCE OF USING THE TASKS
AND CRITERIA OF THE RIRLS INTERNATIONAL
PROGRAM IN DETERMINING AND ASSESSING THE
TALENT OF PRIMARY STUDENTS**

Norqobilova Rayxona Davlatovna
Termiz State Pedagogical Institute, senior teacher
(PhD)

Abstract: This article discusses the definition of RIRLS, the two types of reading most often used by students in the classroom, four groups of reading skills in reading literary and popular science texts. is conducted.

Key words: RIRLS, gaining experience, obtaining and using information, copying, building, induction, deduction, proof.

In the process of reforming the education system in our country, it is important to form the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students based on state educational standards and to improve the evaluation system based on advanced foreign experiences, international criteria and requirements. Currently, according to the definition of RIRLS, reading literacy is the ability to understand and use the various forms of language required by society and valued by people, as well as the ability to create meaning from texts in various forms.

RIRLS is a study monitoring the quality of reading in countries with different educational systems. They are research methods that allow comparing and comparing the quality of reading and the level of text comprehension of primary school students in different countries, as well as changes in the education system of different countries.

In the framework of RIRLS research, the quality of reading and the level of understanding of the read text of the 4th grade graduates of countries with different education systems are studied. It is important to select 4th grade students for the research, so that in the fourth year of study, students have a higher level of reading, to form their ability to acquire knowledge in further education, and thus to the

present time. promotes successful adaptation. Darsda o'quvchilar tomonidan eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan o'qishning quyidagi ikki turi o'rganiladi:

1. Reading for the purpose of acquiring literary reading skills.
2. Reading to understand the content and apply it in practice.

The following four groups of reading skills are assessed when reading scientific and popular science texts:

1. Ability to find information presented in a clear form.
2. Forming conclusions.
3. Ability to summarize information.

4. To be able to analyze and evaluate the content, language features, structure of the text.

RIRLS focuses on two overarching goals for student learning, both in and out of the classroom. Reading is all about gaining experience and learning and using it. Both goals of reading literacy are important for young learners. That's why RIRLS aims to make the texts equal in evaluating each type of reading.

Gaining experience. To understand and appreciate literature, every student must understand the language and know the literary forms. For young students, such literature can provide an opportunity to study situations and feelings that have not yet occurred. The events, actions and consequences described in the literature allow the students to not only imagine the real life, but also indirectly feel and reflect the situations they can imagine. The primary form of fiction used in RIRLS is narrative based fiction.

Getting and using information. Informational texts have different purposes and functions. Although the primary function of an informational text is to provide information, authors often have different goals in mind when discussing their chosen topics. The purpose of most informational texts is to provide direct information, such as biographical information or to provide tips for completing a task, but in many cases the text also reflects the subjective views of the author. For example, the author

may present a brief summary of facts or explanations, try to convince the reader of his arguments, or present different points of view.

It is clear from the above that the term "Reading Literacy" refers to "literate reading" and not a test of reading speed. According to him, it is necessary for the student to understand the texts, to observe and evaluate their content, and to be able to express his opinion. Students are presented with various texts: excerpts from works of art, biographies, personal letters, documents, articles in newspapers and magazines, instructions, advertisements, geographical maps, etc. They display information in various forms: diagram, picture, map, table, diagram, etc.

Based on the above ideas, to ensure students' understanding and participation in the RIRLS evaluation research by developing educational and independent tasks related to students' understanding of texts, observing and evaluating their content, being able to express their opinion, independent and creative thinking. possible To achieve the assessment of the quality of primary education in general educational institutions, based on the practice of international research, the teacher should take a comprehensive approach to the educational process, develop tasks related to the assessment of students' reading literacy, and use them in the educational process. It is important. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the specific aspect of the educational subject, the atmosphere and conditions of the training, and most importantly, the students' capabilities, needs, and cooperative activity. In this case, the effectiveness of the educational activity directly depends on the level of his professionalism. The development and implementation of educational tasks based on the requirements of international evaluation studies is of great importance in organizing the teaching process. Let's talk about educational tasks.

The mechanism of using diagnostic methods in determining the talent of elementary school students is the purposeful rounding of the pedagogical possibilities of the diagnosis of creative talent, the integrative features of the organizational-pedagogical, motivational-value and practical-active processes, and the content of international PISA and TIMSS tasks PIRLS tasks.

Educational tasks are a set of educational tasks that serve to determine the level of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students on the subject being studied. Educational tasks are the factor that motivates students to take active action in mastering educational materials. The system of intended goals is inextricably linked with the system of actions ensuring their fulfillment. For this reason, it is appropriate to formulate educational tasks correctly. In the formation of educational tasks, attention is paid to the following:

1. To determine the level of complexity of educational tasks.
2. To create a system of educational tasks in accordance with the purpose of the lesson.

References:

1. Davlatovna N. R. Indikatorlar asosida boshlang 'ich sinf o 'quvchilari faoliyatini diagnostika qilishning o 'ziga xosligi //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1A. – C. 51-55.
2. Abdisamatova M., Norqobilova R. INNOVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TARBIYA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1.
3. Норкабилова Р. ХОРИЙИ ФАНЛАРДАН БОЛАЛАРНИНГ МАКТАБГА ТАЙЙОРГАРЛИГИНИНГ ДИАГНОСТИКАСИ //Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11.
4. Normurodova H., Norgabilova R. VALUE OF MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY GRADES //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1.
5. RD Norqobilova, SA Abdullayeva. ДИАГНОСТИКА ПЕДАГОГИК МУАММО СИФАТИДА. - Academic research in educational sciences, 2023
6. Norqobilova R. D. Methods of improving the mechanisms of diagnosing the mother language ability of primary class students //The role of science and innovation in the modern world. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 139-143.

7. HMB Qizi, NR Davlatovna. BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QUVCHILARINI TARBIYALASHDA SHARQ MUTAFAKKIRLARINING TUTGAN O'RNI.

Yosh mutaxassislar, 2023.

8. Norqobilova R., To'Rayeva M. Importance of talent in child development. – 2022.

9. Kizi Z. S. K., Davlatovna N. R., Kizi T. B. M. high spiritual generation-third renaissance builders //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 5. – C. 167-169.

10. Norqobilova R. D. COMPONENT PARTS AND TASKS OF PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS //Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 76-83.

11. Norqobilova R. D. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL-PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS //World of Scientific news in Science. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 48-53.

12. Qahhorova M., Norqobilova R. BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QITUVCHILARINI TO'G'RI O'QISHGA O'RGATISH USULLARI //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1.

13. Qobilova M., Norqobilova R. GLOBALLASHUV DAVRIDA MARKAZIY OSIYONING O'TMISHI, BUGUNI VA ISTIQBOLINI O'RGANISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1.

14. Nazarova P., Norqobilova R. Pedagogical possibilities of education of young generation at abu rayhan beruni teaching. – 2022.

15. Xoliyeva S., Norqobilova R. Eastern scientists' views on speech. – 2022.

16. Davlatovna N. R. Pedagogical Basis of Interdisciplinary Communication in the Educational Process //International Journal on Orange Technologies. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 108-111.